

A Review on Fear, Anxiety and Anxiety Disorders

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Abstract

Fear and anxiety have been among the most important problems of humankind throughout the ages. As Maslow (1970) said in his hierarchy of needs, the need for security is one of the most basic needs. People want to feel safe. Therefore, they fear things that are foreign and unknown to them.

Primitive people's earthquake, flood, fire, drought, severe cold and storms; They could not be protected from wild animals and epidemic diseases. When faced with these situations, they experienced great fears. Today, with the advancement of medicine and technology, people are protected from many dangers experienced by primitive people, but this time they have begun to face recent problems. Especially with the increase in population, natural resources started to deplete, and a part of the world population faced hunger and malnutrition. In addition, the resulting chemical wastes cause pollution of the seas and drinking water and exceed the limits that threaten the lives of all living things in these environments. The destruction of natural resources, fires caused by humans in the Amazon forests and in many parts of the world pollute the air we breathe; Uncontrolled use of greenhouse gases causes global warming and threatens the life of all living things.

Keywords: *Fear, Anxiety and Anxiety Disorders*

1. Introduction

As if these existing dangers were not enough, instead of sharing the natural resources in the world fairly, big trusts threaten world peace with the passion of owning everything (Steiner and Şahin 2018). To seize the resources of the oppressed nations through wars, the trusts incite the discrimination of religion, sect and race, leading to an increase in terrorist incidents and the spread of fear, anxiety and insecurity all over the world. Most of the individuals, who are aware of all the problems that have arisen for humanity with the effect of mass media, fear these dangers and experience anxiety for the future.

2. Fear, Anxiety and Anxiety Disorders

2.1. Fear and Anxiety Concepts

Fear is defined as an emotional response to the concrete danger that exists now. The focus is on the "current" aspect of fear and the "expected" aspect of anxiety.

Fear: It is about the concrete threat and danger that exists now, while anxiety is about situations in the future. A wild animal in the forest or a person who is exposed to a big explosion, natural disasters, and threats and attacks from other people experiences fear.

Anxiety: Uncertain how the person will live now and in the future; it can be defined as a state of worry and uneasiness about a subjective situation that is unlikely to happen. Individuals deny, reject, and ignore the situations that hurt them, cut off internal and external contact, resort to defense mechanisms. (“Investigation of Social Appearance Anxiety Levels of Physical ... - ed”) These repressed and unconscious situations and unresolved problems cause the person to be anxious, worried, and anxious even in ordinary situations (Erskine, 2015; Kring & Johnson, 2015).

2.2. Physiological Processes Related to Fear and Anxiety

In individuals who feel both anxiety and fear, the sympathetic system comes into play, and rapid changes occur in physiological processes. The organism becomes alarmed, a fight-or-flight response occurs. Anxiety and fear are not necessarily “bad,” in fact, they are both adaptive. (“Unit 3.pdf - UNIT - III Anxiety Disorders: Clinical Picture...”) With the amygdala perceiving the stimuli coming from inside or outside the person as dangerous, the message quickly reaches the hypothalamus, then the pituitary gland, which is the chief of the endocrine glands, adrenaline and other endocrine glands. This message causes the organism to be alarmed and the backup forces to be activated. Blood pressure, heart rate, respiratory rate increase. Gastrointestinal movements accelerate. The saliva secretion decreases, the mouth dries, the adrenaline increases, the glucagon hormone is secreted into the blood, the amount of sugar in the blood increases, the pupils dilate, the blood is drawn from the internal organs and directed to the striated muscles, the blood coagulation increases, the muscles stretch like a spring, goosebumps (Şahin, 2017).

Differences between Objective Anxiety (Fear) and Anxiety

- *In fear the danger is aim, in anxiety the danger is hidden and subjective.*

- *Fear is proportional to the external danger, while anxiety has a disproportionate danger to the situation.*
- *When the external danger is removed, the feeling of fear disappears, fear is a temporary emotion. Intrinsic dangers in anxiety and the anxiety reaction that appears depending on these dangers are also continuous.*
- *The cause of fear is the danger that exists in the person's current life. The cause of anxiety stems from the person's earlier experiences.*
- *The reaction to the danger that creates a sense of fear is understood and accepted by others; In anxiety, the relationship between the reaction shown and the current situation is unusual and incomprehensible to others.*
- *In the face of fear, the individual consciously takes some precautions to defend himself, while in anxiety, unconscious defense mechanisms are used to protect the personality.*
- *Somatic symptoms resulting from fear and anxiety are the same (Şahin, 2017).*

2.3. Fear and Anxiety Concepts According to Theorists

Objective Anxiety (Fear)

Freud used objective anxiety synonymously with fear. Objective anxiety is a complex emotional response to some external danger to which harm is expected. Freud: emphasizes that the conscious feeling of danger leads to the anxiety of avoiding these dangers (External Danger Hazard Perception Objective Anxiety) (Spielberger, 1966). Cattell and Scheier (1958) named objective anxiety as state anxiety and neurotic anxiety as trait anxiety. Spielberger (1966) examined state anxiety in detail. State anxiety is considered one of the basic human emotions. Everyone experiences objective anxiety (fear) in dangerous situations. When faced with wild animals, natural dangers, especially the threats and dangers caused by humans, it is normal for the individual to experience fear and the sympathetic system to come into play. The emotion experienced in the face of this concrete danger is objective anxiety (fear). When the danger has passed, the parasympathetic system comes into play to rebalance the organism. Homeostatic balance is restored (Carlson, 2014; Kring and Johnson, 2015).

The fact that the factors causing objective anxiety to exceed a certain intensity, the fears that the person has experienced since childhood, can increase the reaction of trait anxiety. objective anxiety:

It is a feeling that arises because of concrete dangers that threaten the life and self of the individual, prevent him from meeting his needs, and may lead to the loss of his prestige (reputation) in the society. For example, the emotional reaction seen in individuals in the face of concrete dangers such as earthquake, flood, drought, danger of war, losing loved ones, being unemployed, being attacked, being extorted is objective anxiety (fear). However, if people experience constant uneasiness, anxiety and restlessness even in ordinary situations, anxiety disorders begin to appear.

Anxiety

Anxiety is a reaction to an inner danger that is related to unconscious conflict and whose object is not recognized personally. Spielberger (1966) explained trait anxiety as follows; Some are constantly anxious and unhappy. This type of anxiety, which is not dependent on external dangers, is of internal origin. The individual constantly thinks that their self-worth is threatened. He sees the situations he is in as stressful and feels anxiety. This is called constant anxiety.

According to Horney, there is a hidden and subjective danger disproportionate to the situation in anxiety. For example, as seen in the anxiety of the individual thinking that he will die from a minor scratch; The reaction to danger is disproportionate to the current situation. The person is not aware of the real reasons that create this feeling.

Kierkegaard defines anxiety as a "disease that lasts until death", interprets it as "the loss of oneself". In addition, Kierkegaard saw anxiety as an indivisible part of life, and laid the groundwork for contemporary theorists with the view that neurotic anxiety arises from the disintegration of the self and meaninglessness. According to him, anxiety is "one of the characteristics of human existence." The dissolution of the self and the loss of existence give people fear and anxiety. Anxiety involves the conflict between existence and nonexistence. In Frankl's Logotherapy, anxiety is the fear of life and death. People who cannot realize all their potentials feel guilty. Anxiety, fear, mental illness is just another aspect of existence. Psychoanalysts and existentialists have argued that anxiety is a natural result of conflicts in the individual's thoughts, feelings, and memory.

Arguing that anxiety is related to bodily balancing, Cannon said that anxiety arises because of failure in efforts to react or regulate against dangers that will disrupt bodily balance. Goldstein said that the incompatibility between the abilities of the individual and what is expected from him is important in the formation of anxiety.

Öner and LeCompte (1983) explained the similarities and differences between state anxiety (fear) and trait anxiety with an example from physics: State anxiety is like kinetic energy; trait anxiety is like potential energy. Like kinetic energy, state anxiety is a reaction to an event that occurs in a certain time. Trait anxiety, on the other hand, is the predisposition to show a certain reaction, such as potential energy. The level of trait anxiety decides the degree, severity and frequency of state anxiety that the individual will experience in dangerous conditions. Individuals with high trait anxiety are expected to show more frequent state anxiety reactions in stressful environments than those with low trait anxiety. In 1976, Öner and LeCompte obtained data supporting these expectations in their research.

The Formation of Anxiety According to Freud

According to Freud, the cause of neurotic anxiety is sexual tensions that cannot be discharged and are kept under pressure. Freud said that the mental images that appear with the provocation of libido are considered dangerous, therefore they are kept under pressure, and sexual energy that cannot be discharged by normal means turns into anxiety automatically (Spielberger, 1966).

In his later works, Freud argued that anxiety has two developmentally determined periods. These are primary concerns and secondary concerns. The first example of primary anxiety is the birth event. The human baby leaves the soundproof, dim environment that surrounds it before birth and suddenly meets a different environment. Light, noise and temperature changes etc. in the new environment. there are many stimuli. The child experiences a painful and extreme tension due to his biological inadequacy in the face of too many stimuli than he can dominate. In the first stages of life, the human infant is helpless and needs external care. It is inevitable that pain and tension arise in the organism because of delaying or not giving the food and care given from the outside. A hungry infant is commonly stimulated by the hunger urge; The baby is not able to cope with this urge. The organism reacts to these situations with its whole body. These reactions are indications that the organism is in pain and tension and is experiencing primary anxiety.

In primary anxiety, the ego is inactive, internal and external stimuli that cannot be dominated cause a painful tension, emotion; The organism experiences this situation passively, as if something had to happen to it. Later in life, experiences like the traumatic events of primary anxiety cause anxiety. When the child learns to control his movements, simple ejaculation responses begin to be replaced by purposeful actions; It can prolong the time between stimulus and response and gains resistance to tensions. The ability to experiment changes the ego's relationship to emotions. Initially, emotions are

primitive manifestations of ejaculation that replace some arousal states. The developing ego learns to come to terms with the emotions; It places the thought process between impulse and action.

After the development of the "ego", the idea of danger arises when the individual pre-plans the actions he wants to do and thinks what the result will be. The ego informs that what is not yet frightening can be frightening. This judgment of the ego is like frightening conditions, but lighter. These conditions are perceived by the ego as a dangerous situation. Instead of an overwhelming anxiety attack, there is a diminished fear that is used as a protection measure. Sometimes purposeful fear, which can help to avoid a frightening situation that is a danger sign, gives rise to the frightening situation. Efforts to prevent anxiety fail. This situation causes a tension in the whole organism that can be defined as a covert preparation for the development of panic. This triggering situation, the ego's feeling of danger, has the effect of a match thrown into a barrel of gunpowder, followed by an irresistible panic attack.

The ego is constantly faced with three separate dangers:

- *Obstructions and attacks from the outside world,*
- *The instinctive and unrealistic demands of the id,*
- *Punishment of the superego.*

Since anxiety is an expression of the ego's ways of escaping from danger, three diverse types of anxiety are developed against three different dangers. These are reality anxiety, moral anxiety, and neurotic anxiety. Neurotic anxiety can be seen in three different forms.

- *Free-flowing anxiety: This type of anxiety is not tied to a particular object.*
- *Attached (phobic) anxiety: Anxiety is attached to a situation that would not normally have an emotional meaning. Phobias are efforts to transform anxiety into fear.*
- *In a panic attack or anxiety attack, anxiety, perceived as something terrible, is the typical symptom of convulsive neuroses (Fenichel). There is no connection between the dangerous assumed situation and the reaction shown. It is usually seen in the form of panic attacks lasting from a few seconds to a few hours.*

Psychodynamics of Anxiety

Koptagel (1984) explained the psychodynamics of anxiety as follows; When the person is prevented from reaching the object of the impulse, he blames the things that caused this inhibition and a feeling of aggression towards them arises. The sense of aggression is not always welcomed by the society, it

is suppressed because it causes feelings of guilt. In this suppression, self-blame, education and fear of being punished by the society when revealing one's aggression or being in a conflictual dilemma (love and hostility) against the accusation play an important role. Thus, the aggression, which cannot be suppressed and released, still is unconscious and directed towards the person himself, and the person wants to punish himself. This manifests itself as anxiety.

The Occurrence of Anxiety According to Rogers

According to Rogers (1959), anxiety is a state of undetermined tension and restlessness. The child expects unconditional respect. If he is respected by his expectation, there will be no gap between the self and the self. However, while parents and others approve of some of the child's behaviors, they do not approve of others. As a result of external influence, the child rejects the thoughts and wishes that are in line with his own existence. But these thoughts do not disappear and continue to exist. As a result, conflicts arise. The conflict occurs between conscious values and unconscious values, which cause the individual to see himself as different from what he is.

As the individual cannot realize himself due to external influences and gives to the wishes of others, the gap between his self-existence and self-concept will increase, which will reveal a frightening situation. In such a situation, to preserve the integrity of the self-concept, the individual will reject the experiences that do not follow his self-existence with symbols. Unsymbolized experiences will lead to anxiety. While rejection provides avoidance of anxiety; It will cause an increase in the gap between self-concept and self-concept, deterioration of relations with other people, and new frightening situations will arise.

Occurrence and Settlement of Anxiety

Anxiety, which prevents the individual from realizing his full potential due to the deterioration of his relations with his environment, takes its origins from the childhood experiences of the individual. Extremely rejecting and humiliating attitudes in childhood; cynical attitudes of other adults during adolescence; impulsive behavior of parents accompanying punishment when punishing; the child's dirtying and sexual games are met with reaction; conflicting wishes of parents; quarrels between parents that continue even after divorce; difficulties faced by the child in his first socialization

experience; The repulsive and humiliating behaviors he encounters in his friendships can cause anxiety.

Children are challenged by their parents, teachers, and other adults to reach the ideal person in society. Children's abilities are not considered. Individuals suppress their own nature to reach social expectations. Children who come into conflict with social expectations while trying to realize their own nature and their own nature while following social expectations may get anxious (Kuzgun, 1981).

As Sandström (1982) points out, children who "understand that their parents' hopes are not fulfilled or are compared to other children always to their detriment" when compared to their more successful peers at school by their teachers, and who are humiliated by their teachers, may lose their self-respect, and become anxious.

Theorists being the conditioning approach have discussed how anxiety is generalized. Fear and anxiety caused by the bonding of neutral stimuli with painful stimuli; They claimed that it became widespread by generalizing by giving similar reactions to similar stimuli (Schunk; 2014).

The child's life with adults such as parents and teachers are of immense importance in the establishment of anxiety. Especially when children are forced for developmental tasks beyond their power, they lose their self-confidence and experience learned helplessness when they are exposed to rejecting, humiliating and cynical attitudes.

The empathic relationship between adults and children can also cause anxiety: Children see the emotions, thoughts and behaviors, physiological reactions, and moral values of the people around them, in which situations they show fear and anxiety reactions, model them and internalize them. The insecurity and excessive anxiety of the individuals, caregivers, who manage ensuring their safety around them, cause the children to be more afraid of the current frightening situations, even to be terrorized and their anxiety to increase. For children who cannot express this verbally, these experiences continue to exist unconsciously, internal contact with painful experiences is cut off, and in similar situations, anxiety reactions and bodily tensions arise for unknown reasons.

As a result, objective anxiety; It is a feeling that arises because of concrete dangers that threaten the life and self of the individual, prevent him from meeting his needs, and may lead to the loss of his prestige (reputation) in the society. However, if people experience constant uneasiness, anxiety, and restlessness in every situation, even in the face of minor problems, anxiety disorders begin to appear. Excessive anxiety and fear cause both physiological and psychological problems to increase.

Unusual Behaviors in Anxious Individuals

According to Horney, the average person can be active and courageous in the face of a great shock. Anxious people feel helpless. This feeling is more intense especially in people who attach importance to the concepts of rising, dominating the environment, gaining power. Even the slightest extravagance in their reaction is interpreted as incompetence and cowardice for such people. Another characteristic of anxiety is that it is irrational. Being under the influence of irrational factors is a tricky situation for some people. In addition, in societies that give importance to rational thoughts and behaviors, illogical reactions are not approved and humiliated.

The result is that people are hopelessly held captive by their fears and defensive reactions. Horney said that hostile impulses are a crucial factor in the formation of neurotic anxiety. People who suppress their hostile feelings avoid the war when it is necessary to fight and function as if everything is going well, this pressure increases the feelings of vulnerability in people. On the other hand, individuals who constantly suppress their desires and desires may have difficulty in controlling their inner impulses, the possibility of losing control at any moment while forcing themselves to control these impulses causes them to worry excessively.

Anxious people cannot focus their attention and become successful because they are constantly seeing their own behavior, exhausted by conflicts, cannot sleep at night, and cannot rest because of frightening dreams even if they sleep. Anxious people are very afraid of hurting others, being hurt by them, they are overly sensitive in their relationships. Therefore, they minimize their relationships by setting up superficial relationships with other people. If they choose one of two similar options, they cannot decide what to do and they squirm in conflict. When they choose one of the options, they become uneasy by thinking about what they have lost by giving up the other. Anxious people exaggerate the small mistakes they make by constantly seeing their own behavior. They can't help but think about the mistakes they made that day and before, and the mistakes they might make in the future, and they stay in constant tension.

Anxious people are anxious even in situations that are neutral to other people brought up in the same cultural environment. In the face of new situations that arise because of slight changes in their daily lives, they panic, not knowing what to do. If there is no other situation, even if all their jobs go well, they find items to worry about by magnifying exceedingly small problems and create an environment for them to worry about. The number of anxiety objects constantly increases because of

generalizations they make against people, things and events in the environments where they are anxious. They discount their own abilities and skills and feel helpless in the face of the above-mentioned situations.

2.4. Symptoms in Fear and Anxiety

According to the DSM-5, a person who experiences 4 or more of the following symptoms is considered to have a panic attack. The attack usually starts suddenly and escalates rapidly towards the top; This entire ordeal usually lasts less than half an hour.

- *There are severe heart palpitations, feeling the heartbeats, the heartbeat accelerates,*
- *Sweats, Shakes and shakes,*
- *Breathes with difficulty, it is felt that enough air cannot be taken.*
- *Chest pain begins with the feeling of suffocation and breathlessness.*
- *Nausea or stomachache.*
- *Feels dizzy, dizzy, feels like he's about to fall,*
- *Hot flashes or the person begins to feel cold.*
- *There is tingling and numbness in the fingers and toes.*
- *Feelings of derealization (unreality) or depersonalization (being detached from oneself) arise.*
- *The person thinks they will go crazy or die.*
- *He thinks he will lose control.*
- *He is so terrified that he is almost paralyzed with horror.*

According to the DSM-5 diagnostic criteria, if the above-mentioned anxiety and avoidance and disruptions in functionality last for “1 month” or more, the person is diagnosed with “panic disorder” (Morrison, 2016).

2.5. Anxiety Disorders

Anxiety disorders are characterized by excessive or frequent anxiety. Except for generalized anxiety disorder, unusually intense fear is experienced, especially in phobias

2.5.1. Panic Disorder

In this disorder, individuals experience recurrent panic attacks—accompanied by many different physical and other symptoms—and that there will be other attacks; They experience anxiety and uneasiness for at least 1 month or more that there will be other mental and behavioral changes associated with the attacks. Disruptions occur in social and occupational functioning. In all anxiety disorders except panic disorder, the duration continues for at least 6 months or more.

2.5.2. Agoraphobia

Individuals experiencing this condition experience intense anxiety and fear associated with at least two situations in which they may have difficulty finding help when they are anxious; for example, from markets, indoor areas, open areas, public transport, tunnels, etc. avoid situations. They need someone to go with them. They experience great distress and anxiety when exposed to a situation they fear.

2.5.3. Specific Phobia

It is a persistently triggered excessive fear of a particular object or situation. Patients with specific phobia experience an unreasonable fear of specific objects or situations. The most common phobias: animals, blood, altitude, flying, being shut down, and thunder. Anxiety caused by exposure to one of these stimuli can manifest in the form of a panic attack or a more generalized anxiety. In general, individuals with phobias experience distress and tension the closer they get to the fear-inducing stimulus and the harder it is to escape and avoid.

2.5.4. Social Anxiety Disorder

A persistent, marked, and disproportionate sense of fear arises when exposed to the possibility of social evaluation. Social anxiety disorder; Fear of looking clumsy, stupid, or embarrassing. Patients fear and worry about choking while eating, trembling when writing, or being unable to speak or perform in public. Using public toilets creates anxiety for them.

2.5.5. Selective Mutism (Selective Mutism)

Selective mutism is the diagnosis given to children who do not speak and remain silent, except when alone and with a few close people. The disorder typically begins at the preschool age (2-4 years) after normal speech has developed. This type of child who speaks normally at home with family members

but stays quiet among strangers may not receive clinical attention until he starts school. Although generally shy, most of these children have normal intelligence and hearing. When they speak, these children appear to have normal pronunciation, sentence structure and vocabulary. This condition usually develops spontaneously within weeks or months.

2.5.6. Common Anxiety Disorder

Although these patients do not experience acute panic episodes, they often feel tense or anxious most of the time and have concerns about many different issues. Minor problems with health, family problems, money, school, and work lead to emotional, physical, and mental complaints such as excessive anxiety, uncontrolled worries, muscle tension, restlessness, fatigue and irritability, and problems with attention and sleep.

They worry or worry about many events or actions for at least half of the day. Anxiety and worry are accompanied by at least three (one in children) of the following: (“Generalized Anxiety Disorder: Symptoms and DSM-5 Criteria - Verywell Mind”)

- *Restlessness or being nervous or constantly on edge,*
- *Easy fatigue,*
- *Difficulty concentrating or feeling like the mind is empty,*
- *Getting angry easily,*
- *Muscle tension,*
- *Sleeping disorder*

2.5.7. Separation Anxiety Disorder

Separation anxiety disorder was diagnosed in childhood for years and was thought to be specific to that period. Recently, however, there has been increasing evidence that this condition also affects adults. One-third of children with separation anxiety disorder continue to experience the symptoms of the disorder into adulthood. However, these symptoms appear in some patients in their late 10s or later—sometimes even early in life. Adults also fear that something bad will happen to an important attachment figure, such as a spouse or child. As a result, they are reluctant to leave home (or any safe place); they are even afraid to sleep alone and have nightmares about separation. When they are away from their main attachment figure, they need constant phone calls or conversations throughout the day.

2.5.8. Anxiety Disorder Due to a Health Condition

Many medical conditions can lead to panic attacks and generalized anxiety symptoms. For example: Brain tumor, hyperactive thyroid etc.

2.5.9. Substance/Drug-induced anxiety disorder

Substance or drug use causes panic attacks or other anxiety symptoms. Many substances can cause symptoms of anxiety, but the substances commonly associated with anxiety disorders are cannabis, amphetamines, and caffeine.

2.5.10. Other Specified or Unspecified Anxiety Disorder

These categories are used for disorders with basic anxiety symptoms that do not fit into any of the groups defined above (Morrison, 2016; Kring & Johnson, 2015).

Anxiety in Other Disorders The following disorders can also be counted among anxiety-related disorders. These disorders are distinguished from anxiety disorders by their specific diagnostic criteria. Anxiety disorders can sometimes be co-diagnosed with these disorders. Diagnostic criteria for both disorders can also be seen in the individual.

- *Mood disorders,*
- *Obsessive compulsive disorder,*
- *Post-traumatic stress disorder and Acute stress disorder,*
- *Avoidant personality disorder,*
- *Body symptom disorders.*

2.6. Treatment Methods in Anxiety Disorders

Many therapeutic approaches can work for anxiety disorders. Some of these are: Psychodynamic Psychotherapy, Behavioral Psychotherapy, Cognitive Psychotherapy, Cognitive Behavioral Therapy, Existential Psychotherapy, Logotherapy, Schema Therapy, Gestalt Therapy, Emotion-Focused Therapy, Transactional Analysis Therapy; Integrative Psychotherapy and others... but since so much research has been done on it, there are many sources of information about behavioral therapies, Cognitive and Cognitive Behavioral therapies, especially in the treatment of phobias, in the treatment of these disorders.

The exposure technique is used especially in the treatment of phobias and some anxiety disorders. Cognitive treatments support exposure with interventions that challenge a person's negative beliefs about what might happen when they face their fears.

Below, brief information will be given about the Integrative Psychotherapy approach and the Transactional Analysis Approach and Psychotherapy (Steward & Joines, 2019).

In Integrative Psychotherapy, as in the humanistic theory, the client; respect, unconditional acceptance, genuine and sincere interest. The psychotherapist communicates honestly and openly with the client. The therapist adapts to changing situations, the client, and allows him to adapt to changing situations. In interviews, the focus should be on the internal experiences of the clients. Therefore, in the therapeutic relationship, the client's awareness is expanded by focusing on the client's physical sensations, reactions and behaviors, feelings, memories, thoughts, decisions and the results of their decisions, the meanings they create in their life, their expectations, hopes, and fantasies. By noticing the interruptions in internal and external contact, the client changes to the stage where he can find solutions to his problems (Erskine, et al., 1999).

In the Transaction Analysis approach, the client's current relationships are examined through transactions. It is checked whether there are psychological games in his relationship with other people. With the structural ego records, the person's life fiction is examined. The effects of the commands he received in his childhood and the opposite commands on the fiction are investigated. In therapy, it is aimed for the person to get rid of the influence of old decisions and make decisions again, and to make these decisions with autonomy, free from the influence of past decisions (Steward & Joines, 2012).

If the client needs, both drug treatment (pharmacotherapy) and psychotherapy are applied together.

2.6.1. Pharmacotherapy

Medications that reduce anxiety are called sedatives (tranquilizers), minor tranquilizers (sedatives), or anxiolytics. The two types of drugs most used in the treatment of anxiety disorders: Benzodiazepines (for example, Valium and Xanax) and tricyclic antidepressants are antidepressants from a new class called serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRI) and serotonin–norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors (SNRI).

Hundreds of studies have confirmed that benzodiazepines and antidepressants supply greater benefit than placebo in anxiety disorders. Apart from these drugs, which are thought to be helpful in many anxiety disorders, some drugs are also seen to be effective in certain anxiety disorders. For example, buspirone (BuSpar) has received Food and Drug Administration approval for generalized anxiety disorder.

2.6.2. Combining Psychological Treatment and Medications

In general, the administration of anxiolytics along with exposure therapy probably leads to worse long-term outcomes than exposure therapy, as it does not give the person an opportunity to face their fears. Treatment of social anxiety disorder is one of the exceptions to this treatment; A carefully conducted study suggests that the joint use of cognitive-behavioral therapy and anxiolytics, rather than the use of cognitive-behavioral therapy or anxiolytics alone, leads to stronger outcomes in this disorder. However, for many anxiety disorders, adding anxiolytics to psychotherapy is not helpful. In contrast, D-cycloserine (DCS) is a different type of drug that enhances learning. Researchers have studied DSC as a supplement to exposure therapy. In one study, 28 people with acrophobia (fear of heights) were treated with virtually two sessions of height exposure. Half of the patients were randomly assigned to receive DSC after exposure therapy, and the other half to receive placebo. It was seen that patients who received DSC began to fear heights less at the end of treatment and 3 months after treatment than patients who did not receive DSC. Similarly, DSC has been found to enhance the effects of exposure therapy in social anxiety disorder and panic disorder. Therefore, this learning-enhancing drug seems to increase the effects of psychotherapy based on conditioning principles (Kring & Johnson, 2015).

3. Conclusion

The age of onset for anxiety disorders varies with the disorder. Specific phobia begins in childhood at the age of 7, followed by social anxiety disorder (13 years) and panic disorder (24 years). In terms of prognosis, generalized anxiety disorder and panic disorder progress with periods of recovery and recurrence, while social anxiety disorder has a more chronic course. After the age of 50, a significant decrease in the prevalence of anxiety disorders has been observed. (“Full article: Treatment of anxiety

disorders - Taylor & Francis”) Generalized anxiety disorder is the only anxiety disorder common in people aged 50 and older.

Anxiety disorders should be treated with psychotherapy, pharmacotherapy, or a combination of both. Both psychotherapy and pharmacotherapy have been shown to be more effective in treatment than placebo or waiting lists. In terms of an evidence-based treatment approach, cognitive behavioral therapy can be accepted as a psychotherapy method with an elevated level of evidence about it. First-line drugs in pharmacotherapy are selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors and serotonin norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors.

4. References

- Carlson, N. R. (2014) Neurological Basis of Behavior (Physiological Psychology), Zafer Şahin (Trans. Ed), Ankara: Nobel.
- Erskine, R. G. (2015) Relational Patterns, Therapeutic Presence “Concepts and Practice of Integrative Psychotherapy”, London: Karnac Books Ltd.
- Erskine, R. G.; Moursund, J.P; Trautmann, R.L. (1999) Beyond Empathy “A Therapy Contact in Relationship”, New York: Routledge.
- Kring, A. M. Johnson, S. L. (2015) Abnormal Psychology, Muzaffer Şahin (Trans. Ed.), Ankara: Nobel.
- Kuzgun, Y. (1981) Guidance Lecture Note, Ankara University EFAM Publications: Ankara.
- "Maslow, A (1970) Motivation and Personality (reviewed) Newyork: Harper&Row." (“KORKU, KAYGI VE KAYGI (ANKSİYETE) BOZUKLUKLARI - DergiPark”)
- Morrison, J. (2016) Diagnostic Guide for Clinicians Facilitating DSM-5, Muzaffer Şahin (Trans. Ed.), Hanife Uğur Kural (Trans.) Ankara: Nobel.
- Öner, N., Le Compte, A. (1983) State and Trait Anxiety Inventory Handbook Istanbul: İstanbul. B.Ü. Publications.
- Şahin, M. (2017) Biological Basis of Behavior, Introduction to Psychology, Hamit Coşkun, Nilüfer S. Özabacı (Editors), Istanbul: Undergraduate Publishing.
- Schunk, D., H. (2014) Learning Theories, Muzaffer Şahin (Trans. Ed.), Ankara: Nobel.
- Spielberger, C. D. (1966) Anxiety and Behaviour: Theory and Research Anxiety, New York: Academic Press.

Steiner, C.; Şahin, M, (2018) Power Games and
The Other Side of Power, Ankara:
Nobel.

Steward, I. and Joines, V. (2012) Ta Today “A
New Introduction to Transactional

Analysis” Melton Mewboray
(England) and Chapel Hill (USA):
Lifespace Publishing